

Corticosteroids on Severe Community-Acquired Pneumonia

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Abstract:

Randomised controlled trials (RCTs) have demonstrated conflicting results regarding the effects of corticosteroids on the treatment of severe community-acquired pneumonia (CAP). We aimed to investigate the efficacy and safety of different corticosteroids on patients who were hospitalised for severe CAP.

Materials and Methods: We performed a systematic search through PubMed, Embase, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, Web of Science, and Scopus from inception to May 2023. The primary outcome was all-cause mortality. Data analysis was performed using a random-effects model.

Results: A total of 10 RCTs comprising 1962 patients were included. Corticosteroids were associated with a lower rate of all-cause mortality (risk ratio (RR), 0.70 (95% CI 0.54 to 0.90); I²=0.00%). When stratified into different corticosteroid types, hydrocortisone was associated with an approximately 50% lower mortality risk (RR, 0.48 (95% CI 0.32 to 0.72); I²=0.00%). However, dexamethasone, methylprednisolone or prednisolone were not associated with an improvement in mortality. Furthermore, hydrocortisone was associated with a reduction in the rate of mechanical ventilation, acute respiratory distress syndrome, shock and duration of intensive care unit stay. These trends were not observed for dexamethasone, methylprednisolone or prednisolone. Corticosteroids were not associated with an increased risk of adverse events including gastrointestinal bleeding, secondary infection or hyperglycaemia.

Conclusions: The use of hydrocortisone, but not other types of corticosteroids, was associated with a reduction in mortality and improvement in pneumonia outcomes among patients hospitalised with severe CAP.

Keywords: Corticosteroids, Acquired Pneumonia.

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Introduction

Severe community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is a life-threatening form of pneumonia with high morbidity and mortality. [1] In these patients, dysregulated lung and systemic inflammation can lead to sepsis, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and end-organ damage. [2 3] Systemic corticosteroids downregulate proinflammatory cytokine production and have been hypothesised to mitigate systemic inflammation and organ dysfunction, leading to improved outcomes of severe pneumonia. [4, 5] Several randomised controlled trials (RCTs) have investigated the mortality benefits of adjunctive corticosteroids in patients with severe CAP, but the results have been inconclusive. For example, in the ESCAPE (Extended Steroid in Use in Community Acquired Pneumonia) and Santeon-CAP (dexamethasone in community-acquired pneumonia) trials, the use of methylprednisolone and dexamethasone

did not improve mortality risk in patients with severe CAP. [6 7] However, the CAPE COD (community-acquired pneumonia: evaluation of corticosteroids) trial showed that hydrocortisone reduces all-cause mortality in patients with CAP admitted to an intensive care unit (ICU). [8]

Materials and Methods

We performed a systematic search through PubMed, Embase, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, Web of Science, and Scopus from inception to May 2023. The primary outcome was all-cause mortality. Data analysis was performed using a random-effects model. Eligible studies were RCTs that investigated the effectiveness of intravenous or oral corticosteroid therapy in adults hospitalised for severe CAP. Corticosteroids included hydrocortisone, prednisolone, methylprednisolone

and dexamethasone. Studies were required to report on at least one of the following outcomes: all-cause mortality, need for mechanical ventilation or development of serious complications of CAP or adverse events commonly associated with corticosteroids. Studies that focused on specific pneumonia populations, such as ventilator-associated pneumonia, aspiration pneumonia or *Pneumocystis jirovecii* pneumonia as well as those limited to specific patient populations such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease or diabetes mellitus, were excluded from the analysis. Severe CAP was defined according to commonly used criteria

Results

The initial search identified 7830 articles. After the removal of duplicates, 4878 articles remained. Of these articles, 151 studies underwent full-text review. Three trials were excluded because they included a mixed population of severe and non-severe CAP but did not report data on severe CAP [9-11] One trial was excluded because it did not report on prespecified study outcomes. [12] We attempted to contact the authors of these trials through emails but did not obtain any responses. Two trials were excluded because they defined CAP severity based on clinical impression without the use of objective criteria. [13,14] One study used corticosteroids as part of a bundled intervention and was excluded. [15] Subsequently, a total of 10 studies were included in the final analysis

Discussion

In this updated meta-analysis of 10 studies comprising 1962 patients, the use of corticosteroids results in a reduction in overall mortality in patients with severe CAP. In particular, hydrocortisone reduces the risk of all-cause mortality. These clinical benefits were not observed for other types of corticosteroids. Prior to this study, three meta-analyses have examined the use of corticosteroids in patients with severe CAP, but the results have been inconclusive. [16] In 2015, in an aggregated-data meta-analysis of six trials, Siemieniuk and colleagues found that adjunctive corticosteroids reduced mortality in severe CAP by about 60% (RR 0.39 (95% CI 0.20 to 0.77)). The authors also reported that corticosteroids were associated with a reduction in mechanical ventilation and ARDS. [17,18] In 2018, in an individual patient Briel and colleagues found that adjunctive corticosteroids did not provide significant mortality benefits for patients with severe CAP (RR 0.70 (95% CI 0.44 to 1.13) Nevertheless, subsequently in 2023, in an aggregated-data meta-analysis of seven trials, Wu and colleagues reported that corticosteroids were associated with an approximately 40% reduction in 30-day mortality among patients hospitalised with severe CAP (RR 0.61 (95% CI 0.44 to 0.85)). One recent meta-analysis performed

by Pitre and colleagues did report hydrocortisone to be associated with mortality benefits. [19] However, these results were likely confounded by disease severity as the analysis included both severe and non-severe CAP. Prior data have demonstrated that corticosteroids can have subgroup effects depending on disease severity. In this updated meta-analysis of 10 trials, we found that corticosteroids were associated with a reduction in mortality among patients with severe CAP. The novel finding of this study was that hydrocortisone, but not other types of corticosteroids, was associated with an approximately 50% reduction in mortality among patients with severe CAP. Furthermore, hydrocortisone, but not other corticosteroids, was associated with concomitant benefits in secondary outcomes such as reductions in mechanical ventilation, ARDS, shock and duration of stay in the ICU. This result was critical because it suggests that there are differential effects of corticosteroids on severe CAP and only hydrocortisone was associated with improved outcomes among patients hospitalised for severe CAP. Overall, the clinical benefits associated with corticosteroids in patients with severe CAP appeared to be driven by the positive effects of hydrocortisone. Whether this finding represents a class effect in that only hydrocortisone provides outcome benefits in severe CAP or a difference between studies was not entirely clear. In most of the included studies, hydrocortisone was dosed at 200 mg/day, which was similar in terms of equivalent dosing in other corticosteroid groups. In our subgroup analyses, mortality outcomes did not differ based on the doses of corticosteroids given to patients. Therefore, the differences in mortality benefits between different corticosteroids were unlikely to be related to dose differences. We explored the effects of geography and risk of bias on all-cause mortality and did not find a difference in outcomes between studies performed in different geographical regions and studies with a low versus high risk of bias. We also performed a sensitivity analysis by excluding studies that focused on ICU patients as the clinical effects of corticosteroids were thought to have greater benefits in patients admitted immediately to the ICU than those admitted to the regular wards. In this sensitivity analysis, corticosteroids, and primarily hydrocortisone, showed a trend towards a reduction in all-cause mortality among patients admitted to the regular wards, similar to the primary analysis. Therefore, the mortality benefits of hydrocortisone on severe CAP may be generalised to the non-ICU population.

Conclusions

The use of hydrocortisone, but not other types of corticosteroids, was associated with a reduction in mortality and improvement in pneumonia outcomes among patients hospitalised with severe CAP.

References

1. Roth GA, Abate D, Abate KH. Global, regional, and national age- sex-specific mortality for 282 causes of death in 195 countries and territories, 1980-2017: a systematic analysis for the global burden of disease study 2017. *Lancet* 2018; 392:1736–88.
2. Rittirsch D, Flierl MA, Ward PA. Harmful molecular mechanisms in sepsis. *Nat Rev Immunol* 2008; 8:776–87.
3. Meyer NJ, Gattinoni L, Calfee CS. Acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Lancet* 2021;398: 622–37.
4. Montón C, Ewig S, Torres A, et al. Role of glucocorticoids on inflammatory response in nonimmunosuppressed patients with pneumonia: a pilot study. *Eur Respir J* 1999; 14:218–20.
5. Tomazini BM, Maia IS, Cavalcanti AB, et al. Effect of dexamethasone on days alive and ventilator-free in patients with moderate or severe acute respiratory distress syndrome and COVID-19: the codex randomized clinical trial. *JAMA* 2020; 324:1307–16.
6. Meduri GU, Shih M-C, Bridges L, et al. Low-dose methylprednisolone treatment in critically ill patients with severe community-acquired pneumonia. *Intensive Care Med.* 2022; 48:1009–23.
7. Wittermans E, Vestjens SMT, Spoorenberg SMC, et al. Adjunctive treatment with oral dexamethasone in non-ICU patients hospitalised with community-acquired pneumonia: a randomised clinical trial. *Eur Respir J* 2021;58: 2002535.
8. Dequin P-F, Meziani F, Quenot J-P, et al. Hydrocortisone in severe community-acquired pneumonia
9. Blum CA, Nigro N, Briel M, et al. Adjunct prednisone therapy for patients with community-acquired pneumonia: a multicentre, double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet* 2015; 385:1511–8
10. Meijvis SCA, Hardeman H, Remmelts HHF, et al. Dexamethasone and length of hospital stay in patients with community-acquired pneumonia: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet.* 2011; 377:2023–30.
11. Nafae RM, Ragab MI, Amany FM, et al. Adjunct role of corticosteroids in the treatment of community-acquired pneumonia. *Egypt J Chest Dis Tuberc.* 2013; 62:439–45.
12. Mikami K, Suzuki M, Kitagawa H, et al. Efficacy of corticosteroids in the treatment of community-acquired pneumonia requiring hospitalization. *Lung.* 2007; 185:249–55.
13. Wagner HN Jr, Bennett IL Jr, Lasagna L, et al. The effect of hydrocortisone upon the course of pneumococcal pneumonia treated with penicillin. *Bull Johns Hopkins Hosp.* 1956; 98:197–215.
14. McHardy VU, Schonell ME. Ampicillin dosage and use of prednisolone in treatment of pneumonia: co-operative controlled trial. *Br Med J.* 1972; 4:569–73.
15. Lloyd M, Karahalios A, Janus E, et al. Effectiveness of a bundled intervention including adjunctive corticosteroids on outcomes of hospitalized patients with community-acquired pneumonia: a stepped-wedge randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Intern Med.* 2019; 179:1052–60
16. Briel M, Spoorenberg SMC, Snijders D, et al. Corticosteroids in patients hospitalized with community-acquired pneumonia: systematic review and individual patient data metaanalysis. *Clin Infect Dis* 2018;66:346–54.
17. Siemieniuk RAC, Meade MO, Alonso-Coello P, et al. Corticosteroid therapy for patients hospitalized with community-acquired pneumonia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ann Intern Med.* 2015; 163:519–28.
18. Wu J-Y, Tsai Y-W, Hsu W-H, et al. Efficacy and safety of adjunctive corticosteroids in the treatment of severe community-acquired pneumonia: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Crit Care.* 2023; 27:274.
19. Pitre T, Abdali D, Chaudhuri D, et al. Corticosteroids in community- acquired bacterial pneumonia: a systematic review, pairwise and dose-response meta-analysis.